

Research Article

Cost Quest: Basic Costing Challenge

Norhayati Zamri^{1,*}, Nur Mimi Aisyah Mohamed Saufi², Ahmad Tsaqief Mohd Zu³, Haslam Hadhari Kudri⁴, and Nor Fadilah Salihan⁵

¹ Faculty of Accountancy, University Technology MARA, Perak Branch, Tapah Campus; norha266@uitm.edu.my; 0009-0005-4808-8448

² Faculty of Accountancy, University Technology MARA, Perak Branch, Tapah Campus; 2023611068@student.uitm.edu.my

³ Faculty of Accountancy, University Technology MARA, Perak Branch, Tapah Campus; 2023874956@student.uitm.edu.my

⁴ Faculty of Accountancy, University Technology MARA, Perak Branch, Tapah Campus; 2023815512@student.uitm.edu.my

⁵ Faculty of Accountancy, University Technology MARA, Perak Branch, Tapah Campus; 2023824092@student.uitm.edu.my

* Correspondence: norha266@uitm.edu.my; +6053742000.

Abstract: *Students frequently struggle to understand the complexities of basic cost accounting because of its technical nature. By turning dry theories into lively, interactive experiences, Cost Quest offers an alternative solution. It develops critical thinking, decision-making, and problem-solving abilities that are crucial in cost accounting. Students can apply theoretical information to practical circumstances through the simulation of real-world settings within the gaming environment, which encourages active involvement and enhances comprehension. Groups or individuals can play it as stand-alone resources in online environments, or as supplemental aids in traditional classrooms. Cost Quest's target market includes accounting and non-accounting students who register for cost accounting courses. Furthermore, it may be used in seminars or workshops for business organizations, such as Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), to help them understand cost structures and behaviors to allocate and compute costs accurately. Through game-based learning, learners can actively engage with the material, apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios, and develop critical thinking skills essential for managerial roles in accounting and finance.*

Keywords: cost accounting, game-based learning, students, small and medium enterprise, innovation

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the constantly evolving educational environment, traditional teaching approaches undergo constant re-evaluation and enhancement. One such innovation is the integration of game-based learning (GBL) into the educational program. GBL uses the engaging and immersive nature of games to support educational objectives, resulting in a more interactive and exciting educational environment. Hartt, Hosseini and Mostafapour (2020) highlight the capacity of game-based learning in higher education. On average, students preferred the gamified lecture, which led to higher levels of engagement and demonstrated greater effectiveness in terms of enjoyment, peer interaction, and idea exchange. This innovative approach transforms traditional educational paradigms by integrating play into the learning process, thereby making it more appealing and effective.

Despite the progress made in educational methods, a significant number of students still face challenges in terms of their involvement, motivation, and ability to remember theory. Traditional classroom environments frequently depend on passive learning techniques, such as lectures and memorization through repetition, which can result in disengagement and a lack of active participation. Consequently, educators have the difficult task of making learning more engaging and productive, especially for students who might not do well in traditional classroom settings. Game-based learning offers a promising solution to these challenges. By utilizing the concepts of game design, such as providing instant feedback, setting goal-oriented activities, and adjusting difficulty levels, educators may establish a dynamic learning environment that improves student engagement and motivation. Research has consistently demonstrated the benefits of using digital games as educational tools. Not only do they improve students' knowledge acquisition, but they also create a conducive learning environment that fosters greater engagement. Al-Sudani's (2019) study revealed that students perceive this format as more dynamic and engaging in comparison to traditional lecture methods. Throughout lectures and seminars, students demonstrate exceptional metacognition by adeptly answering thoughtfully constructed questions using game-based learning.

Researchers in the field of instructional technology have created many theoretical frameworks to understand the decision-making processes that influence users' adoption of technologies. The Technology Acceptance Concept (TAM) is a highly acknowledged concept in this sector and the most well-known (Bujanov & Maier-Speredelozzi, 2021). Ajzen and Fishbein developed this model as an expansion of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) in 1980. It integrates components of TRA to explain the determinants that influence consumers' acceptance or rejection of information technology. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) identifies two primary cognitive beliefs: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Based on this concept, several elements influence a user's interaction with information technology, including their behavioral objectives, perceptions of the system's usefulness, attitudes towards the technology, and perceived ease of use.

Figure 1. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), (Davis, 1989)

In this paper, we will analyze the feedback that students provide in response to the acceptance of integrating game-based elements into educational practices. We developed a product named Cost Quest: Basic Costing Challenge, a learning game, based on the problem and theory. The main purpose of introducing this product is to help students develop critical thinking, decision-making, and problem-solving abilities that are crucial in cost accounting. Students can apply theoretical information to practical circumstances through the simulation of real-world settings within the gaming environment, which encourages active involvement and enhances comprehension. Therefore, we aim to use Cost Quest: Basic Costing Challenge as a more effective and comprehensive learning method that captures students' interest.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The research method employed in this study involved the distribution of questionnaires to gather data. We adapted the measures in the questionnaires from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989). For analysis purposes, this study only considers perceived usefulness and attitude. There are two sections involved. The first section asked about the basic demographic profile of the students. Sections two through two concern each variable separately, rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from (1) Strongly Disagree; (2) Disagree; (3) Neutral; (4) Agree; (5) Strongly Agree.

The primary goal of the questionnaires was to determine the elements that influence the student to accept the integration of game-based learning into educational practices, which will serve as the basis for the product's development. The targeted respondents were students enrolled in the Faculty of Accountancy at UiTM Perak Branch, Tapah Campus. The participants provided a total of 105 responses. We used descriptive statistics to summarize the data.

3. FINDINGS

Figure 2. Perceived Usefulness and Attitude towards Game-based Learning

Figure 2 illustrates the feedback obtained from students regarding their perceptions and attitudes towards game-based learning (GBL). The data is segmented into two main categories: Perceived Usefulness and Attitude. Each category contains several statements rated on a scale, with the total rating percentage of agreed and strongly agreed for each statement displayed. The findings indicate a generally positive perception and attitude towards game-based learning among the respondents. First, the data shows that respondents believe in the potential benefits of game-based learning. The highest-rated statement in this category, "The game-based learning will enhance the effectiveness of learning," suggests that respondents see GBL as a valuable tool for improving learning outcomes. However, the relatively lower rating for "The game-based learning will improve my learning performance" suggests some reservations about the direct impact on individual performance.

Second, respondents exhibit a very positive attitude towards game-based learning, as indicated by the high ratings in this category. The statement "I believe that game-based learning helps me to be more engaged in learning" received the highest average rating, reflecting a strong belief in GBL's ability to make learning more engaging. This is crucial because engagement is a key factor in effective learning. Additionally, the high ratings for the statements "I feel positive towards the use of game-based learning" and "Studying using the game-based learning is a good idea" underscore a general approval and endorsement of GBL.

4. DISCUSSION

Figure 3. Interface of the Cost Quest: Basic Costing Challenge

Based on the findings, it appears that positive perceptions and attitudes toward game-based learning suggest that it could be an effective educational tool. The high engagement levels reported by respondents imply that GBL can potentially increase student motivation and interest in learning. The introduction of Cost Quest is believed to be able to integrate game-based learning strategies to leverage these benefits. However, mixed perceptions about the direct impact on individual learning performance suggest that further research and optimization of GBL methods may be necessary to ensure their effective translation into academic improvement.

Cost Quest's target market includes accounting and non-accounting students who register for cost accounting courses. Rosmaria et al. (2024) found there is an increase in student engagement and enthusiasm, indicating that games can make learning accounting more accessible and enjoyable for all students, including the non-accounting students, who reported that the game helped them understand the topic. Furthermore, it also may be used in seminars or workshops for business organizations, such as Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), to help them understand cost structures and behaviors to allocate and compute costs accurately. Razak et al. (2024) suggest that modern technologies can enhance the usability and accessibility of Management Accounting System (MAS) for SMEs, improving data accuracy, enabling real-time decision making, and overcoming traditional barriers. As a result, this study suggests that interactive tool like games and simulation, such as the Cost Quest, is significant medium for understanding and retaining cost management principles.

5. CONCLUSION

This study examines the feedback that students provide in response to the need for integrating game-based elements into educational practices. It uses a sample of 105 respondents among accounting students. Given this finding, it becomes evident when there are positive perceptions and attitudes toward integrating game-based learning into educational curricula which will be able to improve learning engagement and effectiveness. With the primary objective of integrating a digital game into education, the Cost Quest: Basic Costing Challenge offers a multifaceted approach to learning that not only enhances knowledge acquisition but also promotes engagement and the development of crucial life skills. Numerous researchers support the notion that game-based learning has the potential to transform the educational landscape, offering a dynamic and effective approach to equip students for future challenges. By presenting information in different ways, educators can enhance understanding and make learning more relatable and meaningful to students.

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